

SCALER: Self-Consistent Assessment for SLA Explanation and Resolution in 6G Networks

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Abstract—In emerging 5G and beyond (B5G) network architectures, ensuring service-level objectives (SLOs) requires more than reactive monitoring. It demands systems capable of interpreting behavioral deviations and reasoning about compliance with operational intent. This paper introduces a framework that combines unsupervised behavior modeling with large language model (LLM)–driven reasoning to explain potential service level agreement (SLA) non-compliance. By leveraging a multi-sample zero-shot prompting strategy to generate contextual explanations for observed service degradations, the system aligns intent expression with network observations. To assess the reliability of these explanations, it introduces a self-consistency mechanism based on semantic similarity among multiple LLM responses. This mechanism acts as both a proxy for explanation confidence and a signal for semantic drift. The architecture is deployed in a cloud native pipeline, in line with zero-touch service management and scalable orchestration. Evaluations on real-world traffic datasets demonstrate the system’s ability to support trustworthy and interpretable SLA assurance in machine learning (ML)-based telecommunication environments.

Index Terms—Intent realization, intent-based networking (IBN), large language model (LLM), service level agreement (SLA), zero-touch orchestration, 6G mobile communications.

I. INTRODUCTION

As 5G and beyond (B5G) networks evolve toward AI-native, zero-touch paradigms, the assurance of service-level agreements (SLAs) is no longer confined to fault detection or resource monitoring. Instead, it necessitates a cognitive layer capable of interpreting the relationship between network behavior and the high-level intents that such behavior is expected to fulfill. These intents represent abstract service-level objectives (SLOs) that must be interpreted, enforced and monitored to promote seamless network performance and SLA adherence. In this paradigm, SLA assurance is not only about identifying technical faults, but also about verifying whether the system’s behavior aligns with the declared intent. In the context of B5G, ensuring service-level compliance requires not only detection mechanisms but also reasoning and explainability capabilities. As networks increasingly adopt zero-touch, intent-driven management models, the ability to diagnose SLA violations at a semantic level becomes essential to enabling trust, automation and closed-loop assurance.

The inherent heterogeneity of B5G and 6G network infrastructures has introduced an added layer of complexity

which requires explicitly defined approaches of non-convex nature that are difficult to clearly identify. In this context, machine learning (ML)-based optimization plays a pivotal role in enabling adaptive mechanisms for identifying and mitigating service degradation. ML models can autonomously analyze massive volumes of heterogeneous data to predict network behavior and recommend corrective actions in near real-time. Furthermore, the integration of ML into intent-based networking (IBN) frameworks facilitates a paradigm shift from manual, rule-based configurations to intelligent, intent-driven automation. This enables networks to dynamically align with high-level service intents while optimizing performance and resource utilization [1].

To further address this complexity, intent-driven management [1] has emerged as a promising paradigm for managing B5G services. Intents are high-level abstractions that express the desired state or outcome of the system, without prescribing the specific implementation details. They enable communication across different layers of the network architecture, allowing autonomous systems to interpret, enforce and continuously adapt to high-level expectations. When integrated with ML, IBN allows the network to dynamically align its behavior with specified intents, optimizing performance and reliability in a self-driven manner.

In this paper, we present SCALER, a novel framework optimized for complex, closed-loop decision-making scenarios, leveraging unsupervised machine learning-based optimization to proactively promote SLA adherence within a distributed cloud-native infrastructure assisted with large language model (LLM)-based reasoning. Unlike prior works that treat LLM explanations as deterministic outputs, SCALER quantifies interpretive stability through a semantic self-consistency score, enabling confidence-aware and trustworthy SLA reasoning in zero-touch 6G environments. The significant contributions of our work are as follows:

- Zero-touch SLA adherence framework: We integrate an unsupervised machine learning-based reconciliation approach using a symmetric, fully connected autoencoder architecture to proactively ensure SLA adherence in dynamic network environments by detecting and rectifying operational disturbances.

- Closed-loop agentic decision-making: This framework introduces a closed-loop agentic architecture that leverages LLM-based reasoning to produce context-aware, human-interpretable explanations for SLA violations. By enabling dynamic and adaptive decision-making aligned with service intent, it enhances resilience and responsiveness in real-time network management for future telecommunication ecosystems.
- Scalable and adaptive optimization: By employing this adaptive, self-consistent mechanism in a fully distributed cloud-native infrastructure the framework is designed to adapt effectively to evolving network conditions and user demands, ensuring robust performance and SLA compliance at all levels.

The remainder of this paper proceeds as follows. Section II reviews related work in complex agentic systems. The proposed methodology and the concept of the system model are presented in Section III. Section IV provides a comprehensive analysis of our proposed approach through performance experimentation and extensive evaluation. Finally, concluding remarks and the groundwork for promising optimizations of the existing framework are presented in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

Modern telecommunication networks are increasingly embracing IBN and zero-touch automation as key enablers of scalable, adaptive and self-governing infrastructure. Within this context, ensuring SLA adherence extends beyond traditional monitoring and fault detection to include semantic interpretation and intent alignment. For instance, Diamanti et al. [2] propose a deep learning (DL)-based framework that employs long short-term memory (LSTM) autoencoders to detect deviations from nominal behavior in virtualized and physical infrastructure layers. They also introduce radiographic visualizations and state graphs to characterize anomaly propagation and support reconfiguration decisions within a closed-loop orchestration system. Although they focus on low-level anomaly detection and root cause analysis (RCA), they do not address semantic-level SLA reasoning or explanation generation.

Detecting deviations from expected behavior is not sufficient in intent-based or SLA-critical environments, where the core challenge lies in determining whether the network behavior aligns with the declared intent or constitutes a violation of SLA objectives. Such deviations must be understood in terms of semantic misalignment rather than low-level faults. To support this, network operators increasingly require interpretable and trustworthy explanations that can link observed behavior to high-level service goals. The emergence of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) has inspired efforts to bridge the gap between statistical detection methods and semantic reasoning about intent fulfillment. Bommasani et al. [3] explore the broader implications of foundation models, such as LLMs, for reasoning, explanation and abstraction in complex systems. These models offer a promising foundation for generating context-aware, natural language explanations of network state

Fig. 1: Overview of the SCALER framework.

in relation to intent, helping close the loop between observation, interpretation and action.

Pei et al. [4] present Flow-of-Action, a multi-agent LLM framework for RCA in microservice architectures, treating incidents as deviations from expected operational intent rather than isolated anomalies. The system constrains LLM orchestration at key decision points, mitigating hallucinations and random action selection. Their approach extends the thought–action–observation paradigm with an action-set stage to evaluate multiple diagnostic paths before execution and distributes tasks across specialized agents for multimodal data denoising, historical incident recall and termination decisions. Evaluated on a real-world microservice system with injected faults achieves 64% localization accuracy demonstrating the benefits of structured agent collaboration for more reliable, intent-aware RCA.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The system model in Fig. 1 represents a 6G network infrastructure managed by AI-native orchestration systems that support intent-driven service assurance. Within this environment, diverse service classes such as enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) and massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) operate under distinct SLA requirements and intent declarations. As the infrastructure continuously generates telemetry data, deviations from expected SLA-compliant behavior are flagged using an unsupervised anomaly detection model. These deviations are interpreted as potential failures to fulfill high-level service intents and are passed to an LLM agent through multi-sample zero-shot prompting to generate multiple semantic explanations. The SCALER component evaluates these outputs by constructing an explanation matrix and computing a self-consistency score based on the semantic similarity among responses. This score serves as a proxy for explanation trustworthiness and enables semantic drift detection over time. In doing so, SCALER enhances the SLA monitoring process with interpretable reasoning and trust-

aware insights, facilitating closed-loop service assurance in dynamic telecommunication environments.

A. Dataset and preliminaries

To model intent realization and evaluate SLA violations in a realistic 5G service environment, we utilize the CIC-IDS2017 dataset [5], which captures diverse types of network traffic, including both benign sessions and various violation scenarios. Although originally developed for intrusion detection, this dataset offers a rich set of features, including packet flow statistics, connection metadata and application-layer behavior, which we re-purpose as telemetry inputs for SLA compliance monitoring. Specifically, each connection is interpreted as a concrete realization of an SLA intent, specific to a service type (e.g., VoIP call corresponds to URLLC intent, video stream to eMBB intent). Any deviation from the typical feature profile learned from benign traffic is considered a potential violation of that intent.

To formalize the representation of an intent as a set of constraints, we define $\mathcal{I} = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$ where each constraint C_i denotes a performance condition. A violation is modeled to occur when an observed network flow f_t at time t fails to satisfy at least one constraint:

$$\text{Violation}(f_t) \iff \exists C_i \in \mathcal{I} \text{ such that } f_t \not\subseteq C_i$$

Only data flows that comply with the expected operational conditions are considered SLA-compliant, while deviations are treated as potential intent realization failures.

B. Autoencoder-based Detection of SLA Violations

To detect deviations from expected SLA-compliant behavior, we adopt an unsupervised learning approach based on an autoencoder architecture. The autoencoder is trained solely on benign traffic flows that are known to comply with declared intents, effectively learning the latent feature representations of SLA-compliant behavior.

Given an input flow $f_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$, where d is the dimensionality of the flow's feature vector, the autoencoder reconstructs the flow as \hat{f}_t . The reconstruction error is computed using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss [6]:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(f_t) = \|f_t - \hat{f}_t\|_2^2. \quad (1)$$

At inference time, flows that exhibit a reconstruction loss above a predefined threshold τ are flagged as anomalous:

$$\text{Anomalous}(f_t) \iff \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(f_t) > \tau.$$

Flagged flows are subjected to semantic interpretation, wherein the LLM operates as a probabilistic reasoning agent conditioned on a constrained prompt context. This approach supports detection of both known and unknown violations without requiring prior attack signatures or labeled examples, aligning with zero-touch network management principles.

The optimal decision threshold τ^* is selected by maximizing the F1-score over a set of candidate thresholds \mathcal{T} , derived from the empirical distribution of reconstruction losses:

$$\tau^* = \arg \max_{\tau \in \mathcal{T}} \text{F1}(\tau), \quad (2)$$

where the F1-score is defined as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Precision is computed as the ratio of true positives to predicted positives, while recall is the ratio of true positives to actual positives. Intuitively, τ^* is the bound that maximizes the harmonic mean of precision and recall, ensuring optimal SLA violation detection sensitivity.

C. LLM-Based Explanation Generation

Following the detection of flagged network flows, we utilize an LLM to generate natural language explanations for each deviation. These flows, which were previously flagged by the autoencoder, are serialized into structured prompt templates, containing selected flow-level features such as packet statistics, duration, flag distributions and port activity.

For each instance, the LLM is queried using multi-sample zero-shot prompting, conditioned on representative examples of non SLA-adherent behavior. The output consists of a human-readable explanation that infers the most plausible cause of deviation, such as abnormal traffic patterns due to distributed denial-of-service (DDoS), SYN flooding, or scanning behavior, that may impact SLA adherence. These explanations help bridge the semantic gap between statistical detection and SLA-aware network reasoning.

To evaluate the stability of the LLM's interpretive process, each prompt is issued multiple times with stochastic decoding. The resulting explanations are embedded using the sentence-level transformer model SBERT [7] and a pairwise cosine similarity matrix is constructed. High intra-set similarity indicates strong self-consistency and interpretive robustness across explanations, while low similarity may suggest semantic drift or ambiguous anomaly representation.

Let $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ denote the set of LLM-generated explanations for a given deviation. The corresponding embedding vectors $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ are used to compute the average cosine similarity [8]:

$$S_{\text{avg}} = \frac{2}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i < j} \frac{v_i \cdot v_j}{\|v_i\| \|v_j\|}. \quad (3)$$

This self-consistency score $S_{\text{avg}} \in [0, 1]$ serves as a proxy for the LLM's interpretive confidence and is used in downstream SLA reasoning tasks. To ensure the reliability of cosine similarity measurements between LLM-generated explanations, all sentence embeddings are explicitly normalized to unit length prior to similarity computation. This normalization mitigates variance in embedding magnitudes introduced by stochastic decoding or prompt sensitivity, ensuring that the similarity score reflects semantic alignment rather than vector scale discrepancies.

D. SLA Violation Mapping and Semantic Uncertainty

To contextualize the LLM-generated explanations within SLOs, each output was analyzed using a lightweight semantic matching pipeline. This process involves extracting key linguistic features and matching them against curated keyword templates corresponding to predefined SLA categories (e.g.,

latency, availability, throughput, stability). This enables structured SLA dimension mapping while maintaining interpretability and low computational overhead. These dimensions form the basis for intent realization criteria, allowing the system to categorize each violation in terms of the underlying performance degradation. Thus, we adopt a lightweight pattern-based method to maintain interpretability and low computational overhead, so that each flow is not only flagged as a statistical deviation but also semantically annotated with an SLA impact profile. This allows SCALER to reason not only about the type but also the inferred magnitude of intent violations in a human-interpretable form, supporting operators in closing the loop between detection and resolution.

Moreover, we track the LLM’s self-consistency scores across time and network contexts to detect signs of semantic ambiguity, indicative of semantic drift. The latter is defined as a temporal degradation in the coherence of LLM-generated explanations under similar deviation patterns [9]. If a given type of SLA deviation historically yields highly consistent explanations, a sudden drop in similarity may signal changes in traffic semantics, input representation, or LLM misalignment.

To formalize this, let S_t be the self-consistency score computed at time t . We define semantic drift as occurring when:

$$S_t < \mu_S - \kappa \cdot \sigma_S, \quad (4)$$

where μ_S and σ_S are the historical mean and standard deviation of similarity scores and κ is a sensitivity parameter that determines the tolerance to deviation. Lower values of κ result in more sensitive drift detection, while higher values yield more conservative thresholds. This mechanism enables SCALER to support trust-aware SLA monitoring by distinguishing between true violations and semantic uncertainty, ensuring that corrective actions are only taken when explanation consistency justifies them. The whole process is described in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Self-Consistent SLA Explanation and Resolution

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1: Initialize dataset  $\mathcal{D}$ , number of LLM generations  $K$ , best threshold  $\tau^*$ 
2: Train autoencoder  $\mathcal{A}$  to minimize reconstruction loss on  $\mathcal{D}_{\text{compliant}} \subset \mathcal{D}$ 
3: for each flow  $f_t \in \mathcal{D}$  do
4:   Compute reconstruction loss  $\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(f_t)$ 
5:   if  $\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(f_t) > \tau^*$  then
6:     Flag  $f_t$  as a potential SLA violation
7:     for  $k = 1$  to  $K$  do
8:       Prompt LLM with multi-sample zero-shot prompting template
9:       using  $f_t$ :
           You are a network assistant. Given the flow:
           Duration=[...], Packets=[...], Flags=[...],
           ..., explain SLA violations.
10:      Collect explanation  $e_k$ 
11:    end for
12:    Compute sentence embeddings  $\{v_1, \dots, v_K\}$  using SBERT
13:    Compute self-consistency score:  $S_{\text{avg}}$  using Eq. (3)
14:    Map explanations  $\{e_1, \dots, e_K\}$  to SLA dimensions.
15:  end if
16: end for
17: for each time window  $t$  do
18:   Track average self-consistency score  $S_t$ 
19:   if  $S_t < \mu_S - \kappa \cdot \sigma_S$  then
20:     Flag semantic drift event
21:   end if
22: end for

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IV. PERFORMANCE EXPERIMENTATION

To establish a robust baseline for SLA violation detection, we implemented and evaluated three ML models on the CIC-IDS2017 dataset using an unsupervised autoencoder, a supervised LSTM classifier and an isolation forest (IF) anomaly detector. All models were trained on the same set of normalized numerical features extracted from benign and attack flows. The objective was to assess each model’s ability to generalize under realistic traffic conditions and accurately detect deviations from SLA-compliant behavior. Although the LLM is not fine-tuned on SLA-specific signals, we leverage its pretrained generalization capabilities through multi-sample prompting and stochastic decoding. For each flagged SLA-deviation, multiple explanations are generated using a sampling temperature of 0.7, introducing controlled randomness into token selection. This diversity enables us to probe the LLM’s reasoning space and evaluate the semantic stability of its outputs. As a result, the LLM functions as a probabilistic reasoning agent, where consistency across responses serves as a lightweight, model-agnostic trust signal for SLA-aware monitoring. All LLM inference was performed on a Mistral-7B [10] instance running in a Kubernetes cluster, ensuring low-latency and aligning with the framework’s cloud-native, zero-touch orchestration goals for trust-aware SLA monitoring in dynamic telecommunication environments.

While the CIC-IDS2017 dataset was originally designed for intrusion detection, we reinterpret its labeled attack traffic as instances of SLA violations. This transposition is grounded in the principle that any deviation from expected, intent-aligned behavior, regardless of whether it originates from malicious activity or system degradation, can be treated as a breach of service intent. Specifically, benign traffic serves as a proxy for SLA-compliant conditions, whereas attacks introduce observable distortions in network features such as flow durations, packet rates, or protocol dynamics, which violate implicit service constraints.

To operationalize this view, we trained the autoencoder model solely on SLA-compliant traffic, allowing it to learn the manifold of SLA-conforming behavior. Because attacks often induce abrupt and structurally distinct changes in the statistical properties of traffic, they manifest as out-of-distribution events in the learned feature space. Thus, models like the autoencoder exhibit high recall and precision, not necessarily because they capture adversarial patterns per se, but because they detect distributional inconsistencies relative to the established SLA baseline. This formulation aligns with our SCALER framework, where detection is not limited to known fault types but extends to any behavior that breaks the consistency of intent realization. It also underscores the value of unsupervised detection methods in dynamic, zero-touch networks where labeled violations may be sparse or non-existent.

To further refine the decision boundary, we performed a threshold sweep over the reconstruction error values on the test set. The optimal threshold τ^* was selected as the value that maximized the F1-score between predicted and true labels.

(a) Threshold optimization. (b) Reconstruction error.

Fig. 2: Adaptive threshold tuning (a) and reconstruction error distribution (b).

As depicted in Fig. 2a, the F1-score illustrates the model’s performance as a function of varying threshold values, identifying an optimal point at $\tau^* = 0.0516$ that yields high recall and precision with minimal trade-offs. The corresponding empirical distribution of reconstruction errors in Fig. 2b shows a clear separation between compliant and non-compliant flows, enabling robust detection even under unsupervised conditions.

Table I summarizes the detection performance across models and datasets. The autoencoder achieved the highest overall accuracy and F1-score, validating its suitability for unsupervised SLA compliance monitoring. It also demonstrated excellent generalization to unseen attack types with an AUC of 0.99. To further verify robustness under realistic 6G-oriented traffic conditions, we trained the same autoencoder architecture on the TON-IoT dataset [11], which captures telemetry from heterogeneous edge devices. The model achieved comparable performance confirming its adaptability to diverse mMTC and URLLC-like traffic profiles. The IF performed moderately well, capturing a subset of attack patterns using tree-based feature isolation. The LSTM classifier, trained on labeled data, struggled to generalize due to the imbalance between benign and attack samples, resulting in reduced recall and precision.

To validate the semantic integrity of the LLM-generated explanations, we analyzed their internal consistency across anomaly ranks using cosine similarity. As shown in Fig. 3, explanations associated with higher anomaly ranks exhibit significantly lower intra-group similarity, suggesting reduced semantic coherence and interpretive reliability. This trend is particularly relevant in the context of SLA mapping as lower-ranked explanations are more likely to yield accurate and unambiguous associations to performance constraints, whereas higher-ranked ones may reflect vague, noisy, or conflicting SLA violations. Furthermore, by varying the LLM sampling temperature as shown in Fig. 4, we observed that both self-consistency and SLA coverage peak at $T \approx 0.7$, indicat-

TABLE I: Performance Comparison of SLA Violation Models

Model	Accuracy	F1 (Atk)	Recall (Atk)	Precision (Atk)	ROC AUC
LSTM Classifier	58.1%	0.43	0.38	0.49	0.60
Isolation Forest	60.3%	0.52	0.49	0.57	0.71
Autoencoder	97.9%	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.99
Autoencoder (TON-IoT)	95.3%	0.94	0.93	0.92	0.97

Fig. 3: Distribution of co-sine similarity across anomaly and SLA coverage ranks.

ing an optimal trade-off between interpretive diversity and reasoning stability. The structure of the similarity graph in Fig. 5 further supports this interpretation. The dense, well-connected core corresponds to high-confidence, semantically consistent explanations that typically map cleanly to specific SLA dimensions. In contrast, the sparser, peripheral nodes represent less consistent outputs that often involve multiple or ambiguous SLA violation categories, potentially indicating semantic drift or interpretive uncertainty.

Together, these visualizations confirm that cosine similarity is not only a metric for measuring LLM self-consistency, but also a useful trust signal for SLA mapping quality. This reinforces SCALER’s design decision to incorporate explanation similarity into SLA reasoning, enabling the system to prioritize reliable mappings and reduce the likelihood of false or noisy corrective actions. These findings confirm that our system effectively mitigates the risks of semantic drift and enables reliable SLA dimension mapping by leveraging explanation consistency as a trust signal for LLM-based reasoning.

Table II presents representative examples of these outputs, showing how anomalous flow features are interpreted semantically in terms of potential SLA violations. The LLM-generated responses consistently reference patterns indicative of service degradation, such as burst traffic, SYN floods, or exfiltration behavior, which are then linked to several SLA dimensions. These outputs illustrate the model’s ability to bridge the gap between statistical anomaly detection and intent-level service interpretation. Moreover, the clarity and consistency of these

Fig. 5: Semantic similarity graph of explanations.

TABLE II: LLM-Based Interpretation of Detected Deviations as SLA-Relevant Violations

Sample	Observed Flow Characteristics	LLM-Inferred Interpretation	Mapped SLA Dimension(s)
S1	Very short duration, low packet count and size, high flow rate, PSH flag set, unusual TCP window size	Suggests burst transmission or flooding behavior; potential violation of throughput stability or configuration integrity.	Throughput, Stability
S2	Single-packet bidirectional flow, high packet rate, presence of SYN/URG flags, uniform size	Indicative of SYN flood or protocol-level misuse; likely latency impact due to connection queuing.	Latency
S3	Irregular packet sizes, high transmission rate, PSH flag active, low total packet count	Likely DoS or data leakage attempt; suggests SLA violation in availability or confidentiality.	Availability, Confidentiality
S4	High-rate small-packet transmission, anomalous PSH flag behavior, abnormal TCP window scaling	Matches DDoS or unauthorized exfiltration pattern; disrupts SLA conditions tied to flow continuity and fairness.	Availability, Fairness
S5	Asymmetric flow (backward-heavy), absence of typical TCP control flags (SYN/RST/FIN), large packet variance	Suggests stealthy exfiltration or handshake evasion; potential reliability or compliance breach.	Reliability, Compliance

explanations facilitate operator decision-making and establish credibility in the detection process.

SLA dimension mapping was performed via linguistic pattern analysis and semantic keyword extraction. Explanations containing multiple relevant terms were mapped to several SLA dimensions, while ambiguous or generic outputs were marked as unclassified. This lightweight, interpretable mapping method required no additional model training, supporting transparent and fast annotation of LLM outputs. Across all evaluated samples, over 92% of the LLM-generated explanations could be reliably mapped to at least one predefined SLA dimension. This high coverage confirms the semantic alignment between detected deviations and SLA-impacting behavior. Overall, this mapping capability supports SCALER’s goal of bridging low-level detection with actionable, SLA-centric reasoning. Finally, Table III summarizes the average per-flow inference latency of SCALER across its key stages. Despite involving multiple components, it remains within practical bounds even for batches of 50 flows, confirming its practicality for integration into real-time, cloud-native network management. These results highlight its ability to deliver interpretable SLA reasoning with operational efficiency, making it suitable for dynamic and latency-sensitive B5G environments, ultimately contributing to improved service reliability, reduced mean-time-to-resolution (MTTR) and increased operator trust in automated network intelligence.

TABLE III: Average f_t Inference Latency per Stage

Flows	AE	LLM	Cosine Similarity	Consistency Scoring
10	4 ms	40 ms	20 ms	3 ms
20	5 ms	90 ms	35 ms	4 ms
50	9 ms	150 ms	40 ms	8 ms

V. CONCLUSION

This work introduced SCALER, a framework for SLA-compliant reasoning in B5G networks that combines unsupervised behavior modeling with self-consistent, LLM-based interpretation. By reframing anomalies as intent realization failures, SCALER enables interpretable, trust-aware SLA monitoring using explanation consistency as a lightweight confidence signal. Experiments demonstrated that SCALER achieves high detection accuracy, robust SLA mapping and strong explanation coherence. Cosine similarity correlated with interpretive

clarity, aiding detection of both SLA violations and reasoning drift. Future work will focus on deploying SCALER within fully cloud-native, Kubernetes-based, closed-loop orchestration environments, using real-world cloud traffic traces to assess its effectiveness under dynamic infrastructure conditions. Finally, the integration of confidence calibration techniques and the implementation of more robust drift detection mechanisms would enhance trust and adaptivity in SLA violation interpretation, aligning explanation quality more closely with operator expectations and domain-specific assurance goals.

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